

Hamilton's Equations Within a Quantum Energy Eigenstate?

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In previous notes (1) we argued that the free particle action A (either nonrelativistic or relativistic) may have v (velocity) written as x/t and x and t varied independently to yield: $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ with $A = -Et + px$, the Lorentz invariant classical Action = t Lagrangian. We further argued that one may write eigenvalue equations i.e. $-i \exp(iA)/dx \text{ partial} = p \exp(iA)$ and $i \exp(iA)/dt \text{ partial} = E \exp(iA)$ and call $\exp(iA)$ a type of probability. We noted that if a potential is present one may use $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ [$W(x)$ = wavefunction = \sum over p $a(p) \exp(ipx)$] and establish a conservation of energy equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ such that there exists the same constant E at each x . We described this in two ways. First E represents binding energy so at each x one has the same binding energy i.e. each x point maps to the same E as part of the mass of an overall moving system. Secondly, we argued that E was a parameter indicating that equilibrium existed at each x point, much like temperature T .

In this note we wish to consider a different idea suggested in (2), namely that if one has a quantum state: $W(x) = \sum$ over n $a(n,t) W_n(x)$ this may be written as: $\langle i | H | j \rangle a^*(i,t) a(j,t) = \langle W | H | W \rangle$.. If Hamilton's equations for complex variables are applied to these then:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} a^*(i,t) = \frac{d}{da(i,t)} \text{ partial} \{ \langle W | H | W \rangle \} \text{ ((A))}$$

(2) argues this is the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. In other words, probability weights of the Schrodinger equations (which are complex) obey Hamilton's classical equation.

In this note, we point out that the formalism $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ already introduces operators into classical physics, so it follows that H is an operator which may act on states. We consider the idea of ((A)) as applied to a free quantum particle moving. Next, we apply ((A)) to a quantum bound state and argue that a classical Hamilton's equation applied to $d/dt a(p) \text{ partial}$ may describe equilibrium. Finally ((A)) may be applied to a sum of eigenstates, but this is already shown in (2).

Flux/Flow Equations

As a first step we consider the flux/flow steps for a classical free particle (no acceleration). We have shown in (1) that these may be written in terms of derivatives (operators) i.e.

$$d/dx \text{ partial} A = p \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ partial} A = -E \quad \text{where} \quad A = -Et + px \quad \text{((1))}$$

A is the classical action = t Lagrangian (free) and applies to both the nonrelativistic: $t p^2/2m$ case and relativistic $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) if v is written as x/t and x and t varied independently.

$P = dL/dv$ Here $v=x/t$ and x and t are independent for a free particle so:

$$P = dL/dx \text{ (partial)} (dx/dv) = t dL/dx \text{ (partial)} \quad \text{or} \quad dA/dx \text{ (partial)} \quad (x,t \text{ independent})$$

For the case of Lagrange's equation d/dt full dL/dv partial - dL/dx partial and Hamilton's equations, one does not use the $v=x/t$ separation approach, but the usual classical mechanical approach $H=pp/2m$ and $L=mvv/2$ for a free particle. This is different from using $A=tL$ and treating x and t in $v=x/t$ as independent variables and only using first order derivatives. Nevertheless: $dA/dt = -E$ is reminiscent of Hamilton's equation as will be seen in the next sections.

Hamilton's Equations and Quantum Mechanics

In (2) it is suggested that one may consider a quantum wavefunction:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \quad a_n(t) W_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

In terms of Hamilton's equations. I.e. it is suggested that:

$$\langle W | H | W \rangle = E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i,j \quad a_j^*(t) \langle i | H | j \rangle a_i(t) \quad ((3))$$

This is of a form in which Hamilton's equations with i/dt partial instead of d/dt may be applied to the variables $a_j^*(t)$ and $a_i(t)$ which are linked to probability. In (2) it is shown that using variables $z=1/\sqrt{2}[q+ip]$ and z^* leads to Hamilton's equations in z and z^* :

$$i \frac{dz}{dt} \text{ partial} = dH/dz^* \text{ partial} \quad \text{and} \quad -i \frac{dz^*}{dt} = dH/z \quad ((4)) \quad \text{so } i/dt \text{ replacing the usual } d/dt \text{ is argued in this way.}$$

$$\text{Using } ((3)) \text{ yields:} \quad i \frac{da_i(t)}{dt} \text{ partial} = dH/da_i^*(t) \text{ partial} = a_i(t) H_{ii} \quad ((4))$$

If $H_{ii}=e_i$ then $a_i(t) = \exp(-H_{ii} t)$ or the usual quantum factor. We try to extend this approach to both a free particle and a bound quantum particle.

Free Particle and Hamilton's Equation

We argued above that one may write $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ as eigenvalue equations and that $i/dt \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ is reminiscent of Hamilton's equation. Given the ideas of the previous section it seems to be Hamilton's equation in the complex form. In particular consider:

$$H_{ii} = pp/2m \quad \text{and} \quad i \frac{da_i(t)}{dt} \text{ partial} = pp/2m a_i(t) \text{ then } a_i(t) = \exp(-iEt) \quad ((5)),$$

but this the t dependent form of $\exp(iA) = \exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Thus the so-called probability $\exp(iA)$ satisfies a complex variable classical Hamilton's equation.

Hamilton's Equations and a Quantum Eigenstate

It seems that one should be able to extend the idea of ((2)) to a pure bound state if one uses $\exp(ipx)$ as the state $W_n(x)$. In this case, however, one must note that the energy operator is:

$$H = \text{Hamiltonian} = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + V(x) \quad ((6))$$

And $\exp(ipx)$ is not an eigenstate as it was in the two examples above ((3)) and ((5)).

$\langle W_{\text{bound } n}(x) | H | W_{\text{bound } n}(x) \rangle = \sum \text{over } p \ a^*(p,t)a(p,t) \frac{p^2}{2m} + a^*(p,t) \sum \text{over } k \ V_k a(p-k,t)$ where $V(x) = \sum \text{over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$'s are orthogonal.

Thus applying Hamilton's equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} a(p,t) = a(p,t) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum \text{over } k \ V_k a(p-k,t) \quad ((6))$$

We have listed ((6)) in previous notes, but did not use Hamilton's equation to obtain it. Rather we took the time independent Schrodinger equation, wrote $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ as Fourier series and collected coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$.

Hamilton's equation for complex variables ((6)) describes the time dependence of probability related objects $a(p)$ (note $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$). In previous notes we applied two arguments to:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7)) \text{ at each } x$$

First we argued that a bound state has a binding energy E_n which together with constituent masses yield the mass of the overall system. Thus at each x one has a composite system which behaves as a free particle and should have the same binding energy E_n . Secondly, we argued that the Schrodinger equation represents an equilibrium situation and E the equilibrium parameter which like temperature T should be constant at each x .

((6)) allows one to arrive at an equation for probabilities which does not explicitly use either of these ideas. It is an equation for a specific $a(p,t)$. One may see from ((6)) that $a(p,t)$ depends on other weights i.e. there is not a unique identity of $a(p)$. Thus, it might be unusual giving $a(p)$ an overall different time dependence than say $a(p_1)$. Certainly $a(p)$ is linked to a kinetic energy of $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ and $a(p_1)$ to $\frac{p_1^2}{2m}$, but ((6)) deals with both potential and kinetic reactions. Thus, one may argue that ((6)) is an equilibrium in which the distinct time dependence of the various $a(p,t)$'s is lost because their identities are also not distinct. In such a case one might suggest:

$$a(p,t) = \exp(-i \text{constant } t) \quad \text{where the constant is independent of } p \quad ((8))$$

From this one may show the constant is E_n i.e. that this is fact a possible solution.

Thus one may use a classical Hamilton's equation (for complex variables) applied to a probability type weight $a(p)$ to describe its motion in time and then argue that because an $a(p)$'s

identity is intertwined with other $a(p-k)$'s then perhaps its time dependence is not unique. This leads to its time dependence being $\exp(-iE_n t)$ and to the idea that $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ for all x .

Conclusion

In conclusion we note that in (2) it is suggested that one may extend Hamilton's equation to complex coordinates i.e. $a = 1/\sqrt{2} (q+ip)$ and its complex conjugate a^* . The equations then become: $i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (a) = dH/d a^* \text{ partial}$ and $-i \frac{d}{dt} a^* = dH/da \text{ partial}$. It is suggested that one may apply this to a Hamiltonian using a wavefunction $W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \text{ } a_n(t)W_n(x)$ i.e. $\langle W | H | W \rangle = \text{Have} = \text{Sum over } i, j \text{ } a^*(i,t) a(j,t) \langle i | H | j \rangle$ and obtain the Schrodinger result:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} a(i,t) \text{ partial} = d \text{Have} / da^*(i,t) \quad ((A))$$

One may ask why the Hamiltonian would be written as an operator acting on states i.e. $H W_n = E_n W_n$. We argue that using classical mechanics one may write $d/dx \text{ partial} A = p$ and $d/dt A \text{ partial} = -E$ for $A = \text{classical action} = -Et + px$ (for a relativistic or nonrelativistic) free particle. This form already uses operators and may be extended to eigenvalue equations which introduce free particle eigenstates $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. For a bound system one may consider weighted $\exp(ipx)$'s i.e. $W_n(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

We try to apply the approach of ((2)) i.e. ((A)) to both a free particle and a quantum bound particle. For the latter we find a Hamilton's equation which describes $d/dt a(p,t)$ in terms of $a(p,t)$ and $a(p-k,t)$. Thus $a(p,t)$ is mixed with other a 's i.e. $a(p-k,t)$'s. We argue that for a resonance or equilibrium one might consider a solution for which $d/dt a(p,t) = \text{constant}$ independent of p . This leads to the idea of an overall energy which holds at each x point i.e. $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ where $KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$.

References

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